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Application of Just-in-Time Inventory Management in Construction Projects: A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT

Efficient materials management is one of the key components in achieving efficiency and cost reduction in the construction industry. Many construction companies have traditional inventory management systems whereby materials in excess of what is required are stored. This leads to handling of materials and consequently tremendous amounts of materials wasted once materials have reached the construction site. Just-In-Time (JIT) is an inventory management approach that was first used by Toyota in its Production System and would enable the construction firm to receive materials in the right quantities at the right time. This would reduce the materials in storage and consequently boost efficiency. From conducting a systematic search of literature pertaining to JIT in construction industry inventory management, it was established that there were various research studies that offered insights into JIT and its benefits and challenges in construction industry inventory management. Results indicated that there were various ways in which JIT is

effective in reducing material waste and boosting efficiency in construction industry inventory management.

Keyword: *Just-in-time (JIT) inventory, construction material management, construction supply chain, inventory management, material delivery scheduling; waste reduction in construction, construction project management, building information modelling*

INTRODUCTION

The Global competition has forced the Indian construction industries to look for some new techniques to face the challenges in the construction industry. The construction environment across the world has experienced greater changes, especially, the construction environment has been regarded as one of the most important elements for creating value-added contents for products and services[1].

The construction projects involve complex activities like planning, procurement, logistics, and resource management. Among all these complex activities, material management is one of the most critical factors for a construction project. Materials are one of the major cost components of a construction project, and inefficient material management can cause cost overruns, time overruns, and generation of excessive waste. Hence, effective strategies for inventory and material management are critical for efficient construction projects.

The traditional method of inventory management, which has been followed in the construction industry, involves bulk purchases and storage of materials on the site to ensure the availability of materials during the execution of the project. However, such traditional methods of inventory management are often associated with problems like high inventory holding costs, deterioration of materials, congestion on the sites, and inefficient use of space. Also, the bulk storage of materials makes them vulnerable to damage, theft, and obsolescence.

Just-in-Time (JIT) inventory management technique which seeks to provide resources and materials exactly when they are needed in the construction or production process. The idea of JIT originated in the manufacturing industry, specifically in the production system of Toyota, where the main aim of this production system is to reduce waste and increase productivity. In a JIT system, resources are provided in the exact amount required when they are actually needed, thus reducing storage costs and increasing productivity.

In the last few years, the principles of JIT have received considerable attention in the construction industry in terms of finding ways to boost efficiency and minimize operational costs. Storage space is often a concern in construction sites, particularly in urban areas where land is limited. By adopting JIT principles in terms of materials handling and delivery, storage space can be reduced. JIT principles may also help in better coordination between construction players and supply chain efficiency.

The advancement of digital technologies has further enhanced the possibility of the application of JIT systems in construction. This is due to the fact that digital technologies, such as Building Information Modelling, enable construction project teams to effectively plan and coordinate the delivery of materials to the construction site. This is in addition to other emerging technologies, such as the Internet of Things, which enhance the monitoring and tracking of materials

during the construction process. This has made it easier to effectively implement JIT systems in construction.

The main aim of this particular study is to perform a systematic review on the available literature pertaining to the application of JIT inventory management systems in construction projects. In particular, the review aims to analyse the available literature pertaining to the benefits, challenges, and strategies for the implementation of JIT inventory management systems in construction projects. In addition, the study also aims to determine the emerging trends and research gaps that are available in the literature and may be used for future research and applications.

CONCEPT OF JUST-IN-TIME INVENTORY MANAGEMENT

Definition of Just-in-Time (JIT)

Just-In-Time (JIT) inventory management refers to the production and logistics approach whereby materials, parts, and resources are supplied precisely when they are needed for the production or construction process, instead of holding them in stock before use. The primary goal of JIT is to keep inventory levels as low as possible while ensuring the smooth flow of work and production requirements.

The idea of JIT originated in the manufacturing industry as part of the production system used by Toyota. The system was designed to remove wastage, increase productivity, and enhance the efficiency of operations by ensuring the availability of materials just in time for production. Today, the idea of JIT has spread beyond the manufacturing industry and has been adopted in various industries such as logistics, healthcare, and construction.

For construction projects, the implementation of JIT requires

coordination and cooperation among contractors, suppliers, and logistics providers. Effective planning and coordination are required to ensure that construction activities are not interrupted.

Principles of JIT Inventory

The effectiveness of JIT inventory management is based on several fundamental principles, which are essential for the efficient movement of materials and information. Some of these principles are discussed below.

1. **Elimination of Waste:** The first principle of JIT is the elimination of waste in its entirety. This could include waste such as excess inventory, transport, waiting, overproduction, and defective materials. By reducing these inefficiencies, JIT helps to improve project performance.
2. **Continuous Material Flow:** The second principle of JIT is continuous material flow, where there are no interruptions or delays in the movement of materials in the construction supply chain. Materials are delivered in small quantities to the construction site.
3. **Small Lot Sizes:** Rather than buying in bulk, JIT promotes buying in small quantities that match the immediate demand of the construction project. This reduces storage costs and prevents material congestion in construction sites.
4. **Strong Supplier Relationships:** For JIT to work successfully, it is important to have a supplier that can provide the required material in a timely fashion and in the required quantity. It is important to develop a strong supplier relationship to ensure a stable supply chain.
5. **Quality at the Source:** JIT systems also emphasize that it is important to have high-quality materials and processes in place. If there is a shortage of material in a JIT system, it would immediately affect construction activities.

Comparison with Traditional Inventory Systems

In traditional inventory management used in construction, there is bulk procurement and storage of construction materials at the construction site to ensure that there is no shortage of construction materials during the construction process. Though there is no shortage of construction materials using traditional inventory management, there is also the problem of higher storage costs and wastage of construction materials.

On the other hand, Just-in-Time Inventory Management (JIT) is a method that is

centred on the timely delivery of resources when they are required in order to perform construction activities. In this regard, there is minimal storage and wastage of resources. JIT is a method that is mostly linked to the concept of lean and is centred on increasing productivity and reducing unnecessary costs of resources.

The following table highlights the key differences between the traditional inventory system and the JIT inventory approach in terms of inventory levels, storage requirements, delivery patterns, risk factors, and overall cost implications.

Table 1: Comparison between Traditional Inventory and Just in time (JIT) Inventory.

Aspect	Traditional Inventory	JIT Inventory
Inventory Level	High	Low
Storage Requirement	Large storage areas required	Minimal storage
Material Delivery	Bulk delivery	Frequent small deliveries
Risk	Lower risk of stockouts	Higher dependency on suppliers
Cost	High inventory holding cost	Reduced inventory cost

The comparison highlights that JIT systems are more efficient in terms of inventory management but require strong coordination and reliable logistics.

Role of JIT in Supply Chain Management

Supply chain management is an essential factor in the successful implementation of JIT systems. In construction projects, the supply chain consists of many actors, including suppliers, contractors, subcontractors, and transporters. There is a need to effectively manage these actors so that materials are delivered according to the project schedule.

JIT can help improve supply chain management by improving communication, eliminating delays, and improving logistics operations. By improving the delivery of materials to construction sites, JIT can help minimize

costs of holding inventories and improve the utilization of resources.

The benefits of JIT in construction supply chains can include:

1. Better coordination between suppliers and contractors.
2. Lower costs of handling materials.
3. Faster project completion.
4. Better utilization of resources.
5. Better project productivity.

For JIT to be effectively implemented in construction supply chains, there is a need to accurately forecast, have better transportation systems, and improve collaboration between the supply chain members.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology that this research is based on is that of a systematic literature review methodology in analysing existing

literature on the application of Just-in-Time (JIT) in construction projects. Systematic literature reviews are a methodology that offers a structured and transparent way of searching, selecting, and evaluating from the existing literature.

Data sources

To ensure a comprehensive review of existing studies, relevant research papers were collected from several widely used academic databases. These databases contain high-quality peer-reviewed articles related to construction management, supply chain management, and inventory control.

The literature review is done based on research papers provided by Google scholar, ScienceDirect, ResearchGate.

These databases were chosen based on their ability to provide access to a wide range of literature in construction engineering and management.

Search Strategy and Keywords

A structured search strategy has been adopted to find relevant research papers related to JIT inventory management in construction projects. Various combinations of keywords were used to find all relevant research papers.

The major keywords used to find research papers from literature are as follows:

1. “Just-in-Time inventory in construction”
2. “JIT material management construction”
3. “Just-in-Time supply chain in construction”
4. “Construction material logistics JIT”
5. “Inventory management in construction projects”

Boolean operators were used to narrow down the results of the research.

A large number of research papers related to inventory management and supply chain management were found during the initial research. Then filtering of research papers related to construction projects has been carried out.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

To ensure the quality and appropriateness of the selected studies, certain inclusion and exclusion criteria were followed.

Inclusion criteria

Following are the inclusion criteria for the research papers that were used for the review:

1. Research papers on JIT inventory management in construction.
2. Peer-reviewed journal articles and conference papers.
3. Research papers published in English.
4. Research papers published between 2000 and 2025.
5. Papers on material management, supply chain, and logistics in construction.

Exclusion criteria

Following are the research papers that were excluded for the review:

1. Research papers on manufacturing industries.
2. Papers not related to construction management.
3. Papers without full text access.

These criteria helped ensure that only relevant and high-quality studies were included in the final analysis.

Data Extraction and Analysis

Once the final set of research papers was selected, relevant information was extracted from each study. The extracted data included:

1. Author(s)
2. Year of publication
3. Research objective
4. Methodology used

5. Key findings

6. Benefits and challenges of JIT implementation

Fig. 1: Research methodology for literature review.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several researchers have worked on exploring the implementation of Just-in-Time (JIT) inventory systems in the construction industry, specifically in areas such as material management, supply chain management, lean construction, and

information technology. From previous research, it is revealed that JIT can reduce waste in construction, minimize costs of inventory, and increase productivity in construction. A brief account of significant research work done on JIT implementation in construction is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Literature Review.

Author(s) & Year	Title	Objective	Methodology	Results
Patil & Patil (2015)	Feasibility Study of Just in Time Inventory Management on Construction Project	To investigate the feasibility of implementing JIT inventory management for controlling material movement and reducing project cost.	Case study of JIT inventory control applied to a 63 km highway construction project.	JIT improved delivery operations, increased worker efficiency, and maintained construction quality[1].
Jeong et al. (2016)	BIM-Integrated Construction Operation Simulation for Just-In-Time Production Management	To reduce the gap between traditional planning and real construction execution which causes delays and cost overruns.	BIM-integrated simulation framework to predict productivity dynamics during the planning phase.	Improved schedule reliability, optimized resource allocation, and reduced material waste supporting JIT objectives[2].
Sayed, Ali, & Ahmed (2017)	Need for JIT Implementation: Material Shortage Problems as a Cause of Delay in Construction Projects in Egypt	To examine material delivery issues as a major cause of project delays in construction projects in Egypt.	Questionnaire survey conducted with 100 construction professionals including contractors and consultants.	Material shortage was identified as one of the major causes of delay; JIT procurement can improve material management and project flow[3].
Si et al. (2020)	A Solution to Just-in-Time Delivery	To reduce storage waste	Conceptual model including a	Improved stakeholder coordination and

Author(s) & Year	Title	Objective	Methodology	Results
	for Off-Site Construction: A Conceptual Model	and delays in off-site construction caused by inefficient delivery systems.	data-sharing platform and dynamic resource management system.	enabled optimized JIT delivery through dynamic compensation mechanisms[4].
Si et al. (2021)	A Dynamic Just-in-Time Component Delivery Framework for Off-Site Construction	To reduce delivery waste caused by production deviations that make original delivery schedules inefficient.	Dynamic compensation mechanism using an inverse Kanban system and Genetic Algorithm optimization.	Provided schedule flexibility and incentive mechanisms that reduce delivery waste and project cost[5].
Dharmadhikari & Payghan (2022)	Implementation of Just-In-Time Approach in Construction Project (A Review Paper)	To examine the importance of JIT in construction projects and identify its advantages over traditional inventory systems.	Literature review of previous studies on JIT implementation in construction.	JIT reduces inventory costs, improves resource utilization, and enhances project productivity[6].
Hossein, Tamimi, Kashwani (2024)	Application of JIT on Materials and Labor Management of Construction Site	To analyse the impact of JIT on coordination between materials, labour, and planning in construction projects.	Questionnaire survey and statistical analysis using chi-square test among construction professionals.	Found a significant relationship between JIT implementation and improved construction efficiency and workforce productivity[7].
García-Cutrin & Rodríguez-García (2024)	Enhancing Corporate Sustainability through Just-In-Time (JIT) Practices: A Meta-Analytic Examination of Financial Performance Outcomes	To evaluate the relationship between JIT practices and financial performance indicators such as ROI, ROS, and profit margins.	Meta-analysis of quantitative empirical studies from 1995–2024.	Identified a strong positive correlation between JIT practices and financial performance, especially in large organizations[8].
Bidhendi, Herrera, & Poshdar (2025)	Simulating JIT Implementation in Prefabricated	To improve supply chain coordination and	Monte Carlo simulation and digital supply	Simulation improved delivery coordination, reduced delays, and

Author(s) & Year	Title	Objective	Methodology	Results
	Construction: A Digital Framework for Supply Chain Optimization	optimize JIT delivery in prefabricated construction.	chain framework for evaluating JIT strategies.	optimized prefabricated construction supply chains[9].
Waheed, Abbas, & Memon (2025)	Just-In-Time Importance in the Construction Industry	To evaluate the importance of JIT compared with traditional material management in construction projects.	Questionnaire survey focusing on multistorey building construction projects.	JIT reduces costs by eliminating non-value-added activities and improves organizational competitiveness[10].
Albert Ighodaro (2025)	Impacts of the Just-in-Time Management System in Construction Projects in Nigeria	To investigate the effect of JIT management practices on construction project performance in Nigeria.	Survey of construction professionals with statistical analysis of responses.	JIT significantly improves project efficiency, reduces material waste, and enhances project performance[11].

From the reviewed research, it is shown that the implementation of JIT in the construction industry has the potential to improve the efficiency of materials delivery, reduce storage space, and improve coordination in the supply chain. However, some challenges, such as supplier reliability, transportation delays, and uncertainties, still pose a challenge for the implementation of JIT.

BENEFITS OF JUST-IN-TIME (JIT) IN CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS

The implementation of Just-in-Time (JIT) inventory management in construction projects has various advantages in terms of operation and economy. JIT inventory management ensures the timely receipt of necessary materials in accordance with project requirements. It helps in reducing unnecessary inventory in the supply chain. Various studies have shown that JIT plays an important role in improving material management in construction projects.

One of the major advantages of JIT is that inventory costs are minimized. In conventional construction methods, materials are purchased in large quantities and stored on-site for long periods. This increases storage costs and efforts. There is also a risk of material damage or theft. JIT minimizes these problems to a great extent by providing materials in smaller quantities according to the project requirements.

Another major advantage is that material waste is minimized. There is a lot of material wastage in construction projects due to over-ordering or improper storage and damage. JIT minimizes these problems to a great extent. This is consistent with Lean Construction principles, which aim to reduce waste in construction processes.

JIT implementation will result in better construction site organization. The large quantities of materials stored on site are likely to cause congestion on construction sites, hence impacting workers' efficiency.

With JIT, materials are only available on site when required. This means that site management will be better with JIT.

JIT will result in better supply chain coordination. For efficient communication to take place between contractors and logistics providers, timely delivery of materials to construction sites is guaranteed. The use of Building Information Modelling technology is likely to improve material delivery coordination.

In general, the use of JIT inventory management may lead to improved productivity in projects, reduced costs, and improved efficiency in construction projects. However, in spite of these advantages, there are some challenges and limitations associated with the effective implementation of JIT systems in construction projects.

CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS OF JUST-IN-TIME (JIT) IN CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS

Even though JIT inventory management has many benefits, there are some problems that come up when using JIT on construction projects. According to the literature, the following are some of the main problems that have been found with using JIT in construction projects:

1. **Uncertainty in Building Schedules:** Weather, changes to the design, availability of workers, and site conditions are just a few of the things that can change during a construction project. These conditions that can't be predicted can change the JIT schedules.
2. **Reliance on Trustworthy Suppliers:** Because JIT keeps inventory levels low, construction projects rely heavily on suppliers. Construction schedules can be affected by any delays in getting materials.

3. **Problems with transportation and logistics:** Traffic, long distances for transportation, and problems with logistics can all affect the supply of materials needed for JIT.
4. **Construction Supply Chain Fragmentation:** There are various players in a construction project; some are suppliers, while others are logistics providers, subcontractors, and contractors. The efficiency of JIT implementation could be affected by a lack of cooperation among various players.
5. **Adoption of Technology is Limited:** Most construction companies are still using traditional methods of inventory management. The implementation of JIT could be affected by a lack of technology integration, such as Building Information Modelling.
6. **Site Accessibility Limitations:** The scheduling of materials that are delivered at Just-In-Time (JIT) is difficult at construction sites within urban areas due to lack of space.
7. **Lack of Awareness and Training:** The individuals in the construction industry may be unaware of the JIT principles or may not be trained well enough to execute JIT-based material management systems.

In the above paragraphs, it is concluded that the challenges faced in the implementation of JIT principles must be addressed by improving the planning and supplier relationships and by using advanced technology.

RESEARCH GAPS

While a number of studies have been carried out to examine the use of Just in Time (JIT) in managing inventories in construction projects, gaps in the literature were identified that need further research. The gaps in the literature can help guide further research and ensure effective

implementation of JIT in the construction sector.

1. **Limited Research Studies in the Real-World Context:** The majority of the available literature and studies carried out to examine the implementation of JIT in the construction sector are conceptual and theoretical in nature. There is a need for further research that examines real-world implementation and success stories in the implementation of JIT in construction projects.
2. **Limited Research in Developing Nations:** The majority of the available literature and studies carried out to examine the implementation of JIT in the construction sector were conducted in developed countries. There is a need for further research carried out in developing countries.
3. **Limited integration with modern technologies:** Though Building Information Modelling and IoT can be used for the implementation of JIT system, the available literature on the integration of these technologies with construction material management system is scarce.
4. **Lack of research on risk and uncertainty management:** JIT system is based on timely delivery of materials. However, little attention has been paid to the assessment of risks and strategies for managing uncertainties like transportation time, supplier reliability, etc.
5. **Limited focus on small and medium construction firms:** The existing literature is mainly based on the implementation of JIT system in large construction firms, while the implementation of JIT system in small and medium-sized construction firms is not well explored.

Research gaps like these will help us gain valuable insights on how we can

improve the implementation of JIT inventory management systems.

CONCLUSION

Just in Time (JIT) inventory management has been identified as a promising concept for effective material management in construction projects. From the reviewed literature, it is revealed that JIT system implementation in construction sites may reduce inventory holding costs, minimize waste, organize construction sites, and improve coordination in the construction supply chain. The implementation of JIT in association with other modern management concepts like Lean Construction may ensure smooth flow of materials in construction sites, leading to increased productivity in construction activities.

It is revealed from the reviewed literature that several challenges may arise in implementing JIT in construction projects, such as project uncertainty, fragmented supply chain, transportation, and availability of reliable sources for procurement. The implementation of modern technologies like Building Information Modelling (BIM) may be useful in enhancing planning for material supply in construction sites. It is revealed that JIT implementation in construction sites may be promising for enhancing project performance, and further research is needed to overcome existing challenges in its implementation in the construction industry.

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